

USING AUTHENTIC TEXTS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotation: The use of authentic texts, including literature, as an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) resource has gained wider currency in classrooms, notably in Europe and Asia, where this integration is being encouraged as linguists acknowledge the vital importance of lexical knowledge to foreign language acquisition. The adoption of communicative language teaching (CLT) methods, pointing to a shift away from teacher-centric models of language pedagogy, has also led to a greater emphasis being placed on the use of authentic texts, including literature, which has, in turn, given rise to debates regarding appropriate teaching techniques, methodology and text selection.

Key words: language education, EFL, text selection, language skills, literary texts, communicative competence, teaching methods.

Currently, English language teaching is an important part of the curriculum in Russian schools and universities. In universities, for example, knowledge of foreign languages is often required for admission to the faculties of humanities and socio-economic sciences, although students still do not always acquire competencies sufficient for free communication in a foreign language in broader contexts [1]. In schools, English language instruction usually begins in the 2nd grade, and the curriculum is mainly aimed at developing communicative competence and skills in using language in interpersonal and intercultural interaction. The teacher of English has also changed — his position in society, his socio-demographic status. S. Ter-Minasova notes that among English teachers today there are many who left their former non-educational jobs to teach English. Many of them do not have the qualifications necessary to teach the language. According to S. Ter-Minasova, such an expansion of the teaching staff occurred because teaching English has become profitable and prestigious. As a result, "the modern English teacher in Uzbekistan is less educated in terms of theory and more pragmatically oriented" [2, 453].

The selection of literary texts for teaching a foreign language is a multi-stage process, and it crucially depends on the criteria on which those specialists,

including teachers, who are engaged in this selection evaluate literature [3]. Some suggest that literature should be considered only the works of great authors who not only stood the test of time, but also made a serious contribution to the study of human nature, while others recognize the relativity of any assessments and the dependence of the value of a work on the mores of a given historical period [4].

So, the selection of texts can be based on different criteria and for different purposes. Therefore, before asking teachers about which texts they use, it is very important to understand how they generally relate to literature — as works of lasting significance or as texts with certain functional properties that more or less meet the needs of the teacher and students. Important selection criteria are the correspondence of the lexical complexity of the text to the level of language training of students [5], as well as the ability to ensure effective interaction between the text, the setting and the reader in relation to this text [6]. D. Colley and S. Slater believe that teachers should take into account both the cultural significance of the text and its ability to interest students [7]. They place special emphasis on such characteristics of the text as the personal significance of its content for students. A. Maley also strongly recommends that the selection of texts be based primarily on the interests of students [8].

As for the age of the texts, N. Zagryadskaya [9, 22] considers it possible to use works from different eras, although the texts of the XX and XXI centuries are, in her opinion, the most effective in teaching English, since they are "chronologically closer to our time, arouse great interest among students and encourage them to participate in discussions, expressing their attitude to the events described".

Thus, when selecting texts, you need to take into account a lot of It is not surprising that it is often difficult to make a choice. I. Morozova believes that teachers face serious problems when choosing texts for learning English, since their personal preferences differ greatly from the literary tastes of their students [10]. She recommends selecting texts by "trial and error" [Ibid., 327] and consult with colleagues more often — so, in her opinion, the teacher will be able to take into account the abilities and interests of students as much as possible, as well as to ensure that the linguistic and cultural content of the text corresponds to the general curriculum of schools and universities.

Adherents of the linguistic approach strive to integrate literature into language teaching in order to form a learning environment that is characterized by an active and central position of students in the classroom. Working with

fragments of literary works, students not only improve their knowledge of English, but also develop critical thinking and train text interpretation skills. Within the framework of the linguistic approach to teaching a foreign language, such forms of work with text are used as retelling the content, filling in gaps in the text, discussing what has been read, making assumptions about how the story will end, writing a text other than the author's ending [11], as well as role—playing games based on the plot of what has been read and comprehension tests - choosing the most appropriate title for the text or the most accurate summary [12]. Another option for using literary works is an in—depth analysis of literary texts from the point of view of the peculiarities of their language. There are quite a lot of options for implementing a linguistic approach to teaching a foreign language, and literature in it can be used for different purposes: as a purely linguistic resource or as a material, the stylistic analysis of which allows to achieve a deeper understanding of the meaning of what is read [Lazar, 1993].

In recent years, several publications have appeared on the experience of using a linguistic approach in teaching English in universities. For example, S. Pitina [13] found that the interviewed teachers are satisfied with the results of the discourse methodology as a variant of the linguistic approach to teaching English using literary texts. In their opinion, this technique is effective for the development of all basic language skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening, since it involves the study of authentic samples of spoken and written discourses.

The cultural approach is considered the most traditional in the study of literary works [Lazar, 1993]. When using it, unlike the linguistic approach, the student receives information about the historical and socio-political conditions in which the text was written, studies ideological trends and special cultures reflected in the text, learns details about the writer's life, about contemporary literary movements and directions of philosophical and religious research. Within the framework of a cultural approach to the study of literary works, such techniques are used as a story about the biography of the author, about the main periods of his work, an explanation of the main features of the literary direction to which this work belongs. Students are shown a portrait of the author, photographs of people or places that inspired the writer. L. Anosova [14 p. 16-17] recommends using a cultural approach in teaching English. She prefers poetic works, including sonnets by W. Shakespeare, and introduces students to the history of the creation of the work and the era in which it was written.

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